

Paris 2024 Olympic and Paralympic Games and the fight against doping

On your marks, set...conform!

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Abstract

In the process of standardizing international anti-doping regulations implemented by the World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA) since 1999, the award of the 2024 Olympic and Paralympic Games to France on 13 September 2017 marks a turning point. Audits, decrees, constitutional amendments, structural changes to the institutions in charge of the fight against doping in France, the dissemination and development of vigilance systems, are some of the first legacies of the Paris 2024 Games. Since 2018, organizing this event, without neglecting the significance of the ‘Russian affair’, has meant transforming the anti-doping policy to strengthen the French government’s compliance with the UNESCO International Convention against Doping in Sport and the French Anti-Doping Agency’s (AFLD) compliance with WADA’s World Anti-Doping Code and its international standards. This article therefore analyzes the political, institutional, legal, technical and practical consequences of a binding catalyst agenda (Hassenteufel, 2010) induced by the adoption of an institutional agenda over and above a systemic one (Cobb & Elder, 1983). This study is based on a qualitative methodology built from the analysis of heterogeneous sources: the press, national and international legislative and institutional texts, semi-structured interviews and observations.

Keywords : sport, anti-doping, international regulation, standardization process, olympic legacies, policy transfer.

Introduction

On September 13, 2017, the International Olympic Committee awarded France the organization of the 2024 Olympic and Paralympic Games (OPG). Alongside preparing athletes and organizing the event, a political and institutional competition began to ensure that France would fully meet international compliance requirements in the fight against doping.

Without revisiting the conditions of its creation (Demeslay and Trabal 2007; Hanstad, Smith, and Waddington 2008), since November 10, 1999, the World Anti-Doping Agency (WADA) has taken on the task of harmonizing regulations and legislation in the fight against doping. From its inception, the Agency has been uniquely composed of and funded equally by representatives of the Olympic Movement (as defined by Miège 1993) and public authorities. In brief, WADA's World Anti-Doping Program consists of the World Anti-Doping Code (the first of which came into effect in 2004), international standards, and guidelines (formerly models of best practices).

In practice, members of the Olympic Movement can ratify the World Anti-Doping Code precisely because WADA is a Swiss private law foundation. International sports federations then incorporate the provisions of the Code into their own regulations, and athletes are subsequently subject to these rules, with WADA members ensuring compliance. On the public authorities' side, however, the Code does not carry the weight of international law since it originates from a private foundation. This is why the UNESCO International Convention against Doping in Sport was drafted and adopted in 2005. The ratification, acceptance, approval, or adherence to this convention by State Parties allows them to align their national legislation with WADA's World Anti-Doping Code and its standards since 2007. UNESCO has also developed a compliance assessment tool for its member states. Notably, this convention was the first in UNESCO's history to be ratified by a large number of governments in a short time

after its adoption. Additionally, by 2024, 192 State Parties have ratified it what makes it UNESCO's second most ratified convention; the World Heritage Convention, adopted by UNESCO's General Conference on November 16, 1972, remains the most ratified to date.

Among the key components of WADA's governance structure, National Anti-Doping Organizations (NADOs) are responsible for implementing WADA's World Anti-Doping Program at the national level. In France, since 2006, the NADO is the French Anti-Doping Agency (AFLD), a signatory of the World Anti-Doping Code, primarily funded by the State, and the entity tasked with overseeing anti-doping efforts for the Paris 2024 Games.

These structural and institutional elements broadly outline the landscape of doping regulation in international sports. Recent studies, sometimes from a comparative perspective, analyze the implementation of certain aspects of international anti-doping policy in a few countries, such as the Scandinavian nations (Hanstad and Skille 2008; Wagner and Hanstad 2011), Slovenia (Kustec Lipicer and McArdle 2014), Brazil (Vasques 2018), South Africa, Algeria, Colombia (Zubizarreta 2021), and France (Le Noé and Trabal 2009). These analyses highlight the need to move beyond descriptive and prescriptive aspects to concretely address how local organizations adapt international norms to their national contexts (Hanstad, Skille and Loland 2010).

Since 2017, however, the organization of the Paris 2024 Games has created the conditions and reinforced the legitimacy of importing anti-doping policies into France, including rules, norms, and standards. Thus, the original issue this contribution addresses lies precisely in understanding and explaining the conditions, challenges, and mechanisms involved in transferring private policy instruments into French public policy in the fight against doping, within the international context of the 2024 Olympic and Paralympic Games. Moreover, this article will answer the following underlying questions: To what extent has the organization of the Olympic and Paralympic Games (OPG) reshaped the approach to doping in France? How does this event reveal specific characteristics of French politics and the governing mechanisms

at play? Finally, what are the initial legacies of the Paris 2024 Games regarding anti-doping efforts?

We structured the article as follows. The following section presents the theoretical framework, which both aligns with *policy transfer studies* and extends them by incorporating concepts from pragmatic sociology. Afterward, a new section outlines the methods and diverse sources we used to build the analysis, as well as how we handled them in accordance with the chosen epistemological stance. By revisiting key elements of the history of anti-doping efforts, the analysis will contextualize France's position on the international stage in the field of sports doping regulation. In many ways, the Olympic and Paralympic Games offer a window of opportunity (Kingdon 1984) to stand out, paradoxically, by striving for compliance, making the fight against doping a platform for expressing a proactive national policy, particularly in sports, while remaining open to international demands. The extended analysis will shed light on the impact of the event on the legal mechanisms mobilized, and the reconfiguration of prerogatives, frameworks, and actions undertaken. These transformations reflect a sometimes subversive national adherence to the instruments (Lascoumes and Le Galès 2004) of a Swiss private law foundation. The concluding section summarizes the empirical and theoretical implications of the study and underlines the importance of this contribution and its extension.

An extension of *policy transfer studies*

In 2009, Delpuech revisited the forms of convergence between institutions, rules, and policies at the international level that accompany *transfer phenomena*. In his literature review on *policy transfer studies*, the author presents two explanatory factors (2009: 153): “emulation resulting from increased competition between nations due to economic and financial globalization, on the one hand, and harmonization movements within regional integration processes or the development of international regimes, on the other.” On this second point, Delpuech draws on

the work of Knill and Lenschow (2005). The hybrid public/private framework of international anti-doping regulation offers a particularly complex configuration of actors, enriching analyses of international norm transfer processes. Indeed, WADA, rather than focusing on harmonization, works to propagate “identical ways of understanding, defining, and addressing” a problem that has become public at the international level (Delpeuch 2009: 159). In this context, organizing the Paris 2024 Games justified addressing the identified incompatibilities between international directives and French domestic law.

The proliferation of analyses on the circulation of norms, institutions, models, and practices, places the notion of transfer “at the crossroads of several research streams [...]: the sociology of diffusion, the movement of sociological institutionalism, critical sociology, studies on Europeanization, and finally, those on learning” (Dumoulin and Saurugger 2010: 10). We do not aim to revisit the strengths and weaknesses of each of these approaches. This contribution seeks, in line with the reflections of Dumoulin and Saurugger (2010), to embrace the richness of conceptual hybridity in analyzing the transfer process in the realm of anti-doping within the context of the 2024 Olympic and Paralympic Games.

Using several complementary approaches proves to be heuristic in several respects. At one level, the analysis could rely on sociological institutionalism, since French anti-doping policy addresses a need for actor legitimacy. The isomorphic processes, especially mimetic and coercive ones, identified by DiMaggio and Powell (1983), explain the alignment mechanisms adopted by France in response to the governance tools of the World Anti-Doping Agency. At another level, studies on Europeanization shed light on the circularity of multi-scalar influences and the integration challenges at play in transfer processes (Featherstone and Radaelli 2003).

Here, the model developed by Paradeise and Thoenig (2011) is valuable for analyzing French anti-doping policy. The authors examine how French universities position themselves in relation to international transformations (evaluations and rankings of institutions, laboratories,

journals, diplomas, etc.). They show that this does not lead to convergence or organizational standardization of contexts or the power dynamics within each institution. They propose a “typology of this diversity of local forms of appropriation of new forms of action [...] based on how [the institutions] combine the attention they give to prestige and excellence” (Paradeise and Thoenig 2011). In this typology, prestige relies on a cardinal judgment, highly contextual, and an implicit evaluation system, while excellence is measured and validated by ordinal scales open to international comparison. These two notions characterize France’s dual pursuit in the transfer policy implemented in the context of the 2024 Games.

Beyond these initial approaches, one of the conditions for explaining the making of public policy requires taking into account the processual dimension and, therefore, the notion of temporality. The historicity (as Dumoulin and Saurugger 2010 emphasize) of the State’s involvement and changes is essential to consider decisions (or non-decisions) as turning points. However, understanding the reasons behind these transfers also requires situating them, more synchronically, within the tension between different agendas (de Maillard and Kübler 2016: 25) and a specific contextual configuration – here, marked by the challenge of the Paris 2024 Games during a period of crisis. These elements both justify and catalyze the reconfiguration of a network involving multiple actors.

The study of instruments (Lascombes and Le Galès 2004) and the mechanisms of transfer, both coercive and voluntary (Dolowitz and Marsh 2000), helps to understand the (new) forms of connectivity, as understood in actor-network theory (Akrich, Callon, and Latour 2006). Beyond the relevance, highlighted by Dumoulin and Saurugger (2010), of using translation sociology in conjunction with *policy transfer studies*, pragmatic sociology proves heuristic when it allows for an analysis of power dynamics in a networked world (Chateauraynaud 2006). Indeed, addressing the issue of the circulation of international norms in anti-doping, as with other topics, through dichotomies such as dominant/dominated or winners/losers is reductive. Instead,

examining the direction in which norms circulate, the methods of transfer, and what is transferred at various levels highlights the production, persistence, and transformation of asymmetrical relationships, even of control (Chateauraynaud 2015). Thus, this contribution finds its originality in studying how France has responded to international anti-doping directives; the instruments, mechanisms, as well as the people and objects involved, reveal imperatives of justification (Boltanski and Thévenot 1991) and the ways in which they are addressed.

Methods, data, and empirical procedure

This analysis draws on a qualitative methodology based on heterogeneous sources, some of which we collected as part of our research work over several years and others from the run-up to the 2024 OPG.

First, the corpus consists of international and national legislative and institutional texts: the World Anti-Doping Code, International Standards, and investigation reports related to the “Russian affair” from the World Anti-Doping Agency, the UNESCO Convention, French laws and ordinances, excerpts from parliamentary debates, and reports produced by the AFLD. It also includes semi-structured interviews with representatives from WADA, AFLD, the Ministry of Sports, and the Olympic and Paralympic Games. Direct and participant observations during meetings we attended as experts complement the empirical work. These observations took place, on the one hand, during the development of the “National Plan for the Prevention of Doping and Doping Behaviors in Physical and Sporting Activities 2020–2024” in France at the Ministry of Sports, with various officials from sports and/or anti-doping institutions. On the other hand, in March 2023, we participated in a meeting organized at the Ministry of Sports and the Olympic and Paralympic Games as part of the “evaluation of the French anti-doping system” by the Council of Europe. Finally, having been invited for the past three years to speak

at the National Symposium for a Doping-Free Sport, jointly organized by AFLD, the Ministry of Sports, and the French National Olympic and Sports Committee (CNOSF), these events also provided opportunities to gather data through observations and more informal interviews.

We prioritized two approaches to entering this corpus. The first, perhaps the most obvious, involved identifying co-occurrences of entities such as the Olympic and/or Paralympic Games, France (in its various references), and/or WADA within the texts and transcripts. The second, more meticulous, focused on identifying the temporal markers within the corpus. This analytical method, already tested in previous research, helps to pinpoint elements that evolve, as well as turning points and influencing factors in a process. Using the existing dictionaries in the Prospéro© software (Chateauraynaud 2003) – a program for experimental and reflexive pragmatic sociology on computers – we focused our attention on the categories *Tipping Point* and *Graduality-Quantification*. The first signifies a break between “old” and “new” practices, particularly drawing from Chateauraynaud and Doury’s (2010) study on the argumentative functions of the marker “henceforth”. The second category, *Graduality-Quantification*, highlights the evolution of activities by analyzing markers such as “more”, “increasingly”, “less and less”. Thus, this approach to our corpus enables the identification of changes in anti-doping practices through the periodization established by the actors.

French anti-doping policy in the international context: some historical elements

A long-standing proactive national policy

Studying France’s commitment to complying with WADA’s World Anti-Doping Code and the UNESCO International Convention against Doping in Sport in the context of organizing the Paris 2024 Games requires revisiting some historical, structural, and explanatory elements that have shaped this state’s involvement in the international regulation of doping in sports.

Indeed, regulating doping in sports has involved a harmonization process spanning over sixty years (Demeslay 2013). Since the 1960s, the Olympic Movement and public authorities have been working, albeit at different paces and in a fragmented manner, to develop anti-doping policies (Houlihan 1997). This includes drafting official texts that define doping, list prohibited products and methods, establish control and analysis mechanisms, set up a judging body, and sometimes propose preventive actions.

On the sports side, an Olympic Charter against doping, based on the European Charter against doping, was adopted in June 1988 by members of the International Olympic Committee (IOC) in Ottawa. The IOC Medical Commission, established in 1961, gradually introduced lists and control mechanisms, as well as regulations for international Olympic federations, each of which drafted (or did not draft) regulations and regularly modified them based on the specifics of their discipline and their willingness to engage in anti-doping efforts, adding statuses, clauses, or substances to the list of banned products.

On the public authority side, following a European initiative, the first symposium on “doping and the biological preparation of athletes in competition” took place in Uriage-les-Bains on January 26-27, 1963 (Le Noé 2000: 80). Organized under the auspices of the Secretary of State for Youth and Sports, this symposium provided the scientific basis for the French law of June 1, 1965 (Lapouble 1993: 6). From a national legislative perspective, Belgium and France were pioneers. The Belgian law of April 2, 1965, “prohibiting doping practices in sports competitions”, and the French law No. 65-412 of June 1, 1965, “aimed at repressing stimulants in sports competitions”, were the first texts addressing doping issues. The Council of Europe also took the lead by adopting several resolutions: in 1967 (which led to the first anti-doping controls during the 1968 Olympic Games in Grenoble), in 1978, in 1986, in 1989, and in 2000, particularly with the drafting of the “European Charter against Doping in Sport” adopted on September 25, 1984, and the European Convention against Doping, dated November 16, 1989.

However, the effective implementation of the latter relies “on the voluntary adoption by the signatory states of legislative or regulatory measures aimed at preventing and punishing the trafficking and use of doping products. Yet, the initiatives taken by various European countries in this regard have proven to be very uneven” (Miège 2000: 60-61). While the French government applies an interventionist sports legislation similar to that of Italy, Luxembourg, Portugal, or Spain (Chaker 1999: 6), state involvement in combating doping has varied from country to country in Europe, particularly concerning their political sensitivity to sports and drug issues.

Houlihan (2003: 161-162) classifies countries into three categories. First, in a small number of countries, including France, Belgium, and Scandinavian nations, governments have consistently pursued an active anti-doping strategy. Consequently, several laws have been enacted in France before the establishment of WADA. Law No. 89-432 of June 28, 1989, “regarding the prevention and repression of the use of doping products in sports events and competitions” followed the 1965 law. Then, Law No. 99-223 of March 23, 1999, concerning the protection of athletes’ health and the fight against doping, established an independent body (the Council for the Prevention and Fight Against Doping – CPLD), strengthened medical oversight (Anti-Doping Medical Units – AMLD), and defined preventive measures, controls, and sanctions that could be disciplinary or criminal. Secondly, according to Houlihan, for a much larger number of countries, such as Australia, the United Kingdom, and the United States, governments did not view doping as a public policy priority. Finally, in certain countries, such as the former East Germany (GDR) and the Soviet Union, the government actively participated in the systematic doping of its international athletes.

In the 1980s and 1990s, the inter-sport and inter-state disparities in addressing doping in sports led to scandals and denunciations of the failure to uphold the principle of fairness among competitors in a competition (Duret and Trabal 2001). Beyond the ethical considerations, the

increasing number of doping cases related to the use of recreational drugs (cannabis, cocaine, etc.) fueled ongoing parliamentary debates over the years. For instance, one could read: “Thirdly, the links between doping and drug addiction are now evident. The most recent and sophisticated analyses have revealed the possible association of multiple substances, including hard drugs. It was known that drugs altered behavior; however, the debate around drugs has taken on a new dimension with this usage. Again, the space that separates doping from addiction is minimal” (Mattei, National Assembly, 1998). The Festina affair allowed Marie-George Buffet, Minister of Sports, to implement her anti-doping policy by involving judicial and legal authorities during the 1998 Tour de France. By framing the anti-doping fight as part of a broader public health issue related to drug abuse, public authorities strengthened their legitimacy to investigate and sanction suppliers and trafficking of doping substances.

According to Sallé’s perspective, the years 1998-1999 represent a “clear break” in the governance of doping. He asserts that during the 1998 Tour de France, “the revelation of the extent of health risks faced by athletes and the evident inability of federal bodies to prevent and punish these prohibited behaviors justify public intervention” (Sallé 2004: 405). He also presents the creation of WADA in critical terms, arguing that this new body would constitute “a step backward” for countries like France that already have legislation in this area (Sallé 2004: 411).

Starting from the entry into force of the first World Anti-Doping Code on January 1, 2004, and continuing a long-standing commitment to anti-doping policies, France has focused on aligning its laws and frameworks with international governance instruments (Lascoumes and Le Galès 2004). For instance, on April 5, 2006, Law No. 2006-405 on the fight against doping and the protection of athletes’ health, known as the Lamour Law, was enacted. This law officially established the AFLD as the National Anti-Doping Organization (NADO), succeeding the CPLD, and entrusted a bureau within the Ministry of Sports with the responsibility of

coordinating prevention efforts (Le Noé and Trabal 2009). The aim here is not to artificially revive the notion of French political voluntarism, nor the myth of state unity (Lagroye and al. 2002), but rather to outline the structural elements that have characterized the landscape of anti-doping prevention in France for over a decade.

An international context catalyzing compliance

In over 20 years of existence, the challenge of harmonizing anti-doping regulations has taken the form of a massive standardization process (Zubizarreta and Demeslay 2020: 6). While in 2004, the World Anti-Doping Program of WADA included four International Standards (IS) – the list of prohibited substances, the IS for testing, for laboratories, and for Therapeutic Use Exemptions (TUE) – four more have emerged since then: the International Standard for the Protection of Privacy and Personal Information, the one for Results Management, the International Standard for Code Compliance by Signatories, and the International Standard for Education. These standards, not only more numerous, have been subject to a regular and sustained revision schedule (for example, the list of prohibited substances is revised annually while eight versions of the IS for laboratories have come into force since 2004). Moreover, it is noteworthy that the scope of the objects of standardization has gradually expanded.

On a subject like the regulation of anti-doping efforts on a global scale, it immediately makes sense to consider technical documents that aim to standardize a list of prohibited substances and methods, sampling materials, athlete testing procedures, laboratory forwarding protocols, sample analysis, and results management. However, in addition to the attention to the temporality of this activity, which reinforces the idea of a constrained agenda (Hassenteufel 2010), it is indeed the transformation of the nature of the objects of standardization that is striking. The technical, procedural, and protocol-based approach gradually adapted and strengthened regarding therapeutic use exemptions, testing, and laboratories has been

accompanied by a technicization not only of the work itself but also of the working relationships imposed on the signatories of the World Anti-Doping Code due to the binding nature of this type of document.

This standardization process operated by representatives of the World Anti-Doping Agency not only responds to scandals and the evolution of policies and practices in the fight against doping but also justifies the internal coherence of their measures. The International Standard for Code Compliance by Signatories (ISCCS) is perhaps the most significant illustration of this. While scandals reveal the strengths and weaknesses of existing systems, the so-called “Russian affair,” as commonly referred to in the media, opens a period of institutional and political crisis in the field of anti-doping, especially in the lead-up to the Paris 2024 Games. This affair particularly pertains to allegations by whistleblowers, starting in December 2014, of a network of corruption and collusion involving Russian sports, anti-doping, and state authorities. Without going into the details of this complex case, these allegations led to investigations conducted by WADA.

The reports resulted, notably, in the decision of the Court of Arbitration for Sport (CAS) in December 2020 to exclude the Russian Federation from major international competitions for two years. Russian athletes who could prove they had not engaged in doping were allowed to compete under a neutral banner at the Tokyo 2021 Summer Olympics and the Beijing 2022 Winter Olympics. This affair generates international and multiscale repercussions of the crisis. One of the consequences is the strengthening of surveillance mechanisms implemented by WADA.

The entry into force of the ISCCS on April 1, 2018, thus reinforced the program for monitoring compliance with the WADA Code (which began in 2016) by creating a framework for the Agency’s activities, including audits of National Anti-Doping Organizations (NADOs), and by defining the responsibilities and consequences applicable to signatories. This “audit society” to borrow the terms of Power (1997), has therefore been established in the same timeframe as the

entry into force of this Standard, which includes categories of non-compliance indexed to requirements classified as general, high priority, or critical (WADA, ISCCS, 2024: 50-54), along with a framework of consequences for these irregularities concerning deviations from the rules and thus anomalies that must be corrected. For example, these consequences include: disqualification from participation in governing bodies, loss of signatory status, the inability for the signatory's country to host, receive, and/or participate in major sporting events, as well as the deprivation of funding and other benefits related to recognition by the IOC or affiliation with the International Paralympic Committee, suspension of recognition by the Olympic movement, etc. (WADA, ISCCS, 2024: 55-62).

In terms of the timeline, it is specified that: “8.3.1. If a Signatory does not correct all Non-Conformities within the timeframe set in the Corrective Action Report, or if a Signatory fails to provide the required response within the specified timeframe to a Code Compliance Questionnaire, a notice of a Compliance Audit, a request made as part of continuous compliance monitoring, or a Mandatory Information Request, WADA Management will give the Signatory written notice of that failure and a new timeframe (of up to three (3) months) to correct it. That new timeframe will not be extended again, save in exceptional cases, where the Signatory establishes that an Event of Force Majeure will make it impossible to correct the position by that timeframe” (WADA, ISCCS, 2024: 36). The international context at the end of the 2010s thus marks a new turning point in the process of harmonizing anti-doping regulations.

The alignment of signatories to the World Code with strengthened governance instruments is part of a deontic logic. Two comments are necessary. On one hand, similar to the analyses by Akrich, Callon, and Latour (2006), the production, multiplication, and articulation of these new governance instruments – particularly international standards – demonstrate the establishment of networks that define the conditions, modalities, and spaces for the circulation of norms, actors, and objects, and attest to the creation of irreversibilities. On the other hand, the

development of evaluation tools (questionnaires on compliance, audits, etc.) contributes to the identification and potential disqualification of signatories in a state of irregularity and their deviations from the norm. In this regard, these tools serve as means of identifying and reactivating the incompatibilities that do not concern the proponents of the model. The host context and the adaptation costs arising from the introduction of “imported” elements are downplayed in the name of a common cause. The contents and tools produced suggest *a priori* coercive mechanisms, which are both constraining for the signatories of the Code and incentivizing for the states parties to the Convention (Bulmer and Padgett 2004). Beyond this institutionalist reading, these instruments and mechanisms strengthen the foundations of hierarchical relationships that require “partners” of WADA to meet justification imperatives (Boltanski and Thévenot 1991) and regularization.

Conforming French anti-doping policy: a subversive quest for excellence and prestige

The choice of an implementation path that reveals asymmetries.

On May 15 and 16, 2018, WADA audited the French Anti-Doping Agency. This evaluation moment served as a reminder of the discrepancies that persist between French legislation and anti-doping measures in France and international requirements. The period following the awarding of the 2024 Olympic and Paralympic Games to the city of Paris has been filled with legislative and structural measures aimed at achieving the strictest compliance of the AFLD with the World Anti-Doping Code and of the French State with the UNESCO International Convention against Doping in Sport, a timeline that the French agency partially reports on in its 2018 activity report.

AFLD. 2018. Significant events. *Activity Report: 8-9.*

As Demeslay and Trabal state: “The case of France is an interesting example of the effects of the crisis. For nearly fifteen years, those responsible for anti-doping efforts insisted that the World Anti-Doping Code was unconstitutional. The automaticity of sanctions, the possibility of conducting nighttime tests, and the recognition of the CAS based in Switzerland as an appeals body were deemed incompatible with national law” (2019: 101). However, leading up to the Paris Olympic and Paralympic Games, and while the UNESCO International Convention has a non-binding character, France made a nearly literal transposition of the World Code. In this regard, Dominique Laurent, then President of the AFLD, stated as early as 2019 that France had chosen to fully align with the international framework for combating doping. Furthermore, Chaussard (2024) emphasizes that this is a chosen path of implementation, one that is not unique and, moreover, is not followed by all the State Parties to the UNESCO Convention. On this point, the continuum of mechanisms from voluntary to coercive transfers benefits from being enriched by the concept of *emprise*, precisely because “any system of *emprise* that operates

sustainably relies on the quest for legitimacy of the actors who co-produce it and who maintain its functioning” (Chateauraynaud 2015).

Legal mechanisms as levers for enforced compliance

The data we collected indicate an acceleration in the procedures for transposing the World Anti-Doping Code into French domestic law.

Article 38 of the French Constitution states the following:

“The Government may, for the execution of its program, request from Parliament the authorization to take measures by ordinance, for a limited time, that normally fall within the domain of the law. The ordinances are adopted in the Council of Ministers after consulting the Council of State. They come into effect as soon as they are published but become null and void if the bill for ratification is not submitted to Parliament before the date set by the enabling law. They can only be ratified in an express manner. Upon the expiration of the time limit mentioned in the first paragraph of this article, the ordinances can only be amended by law in matters that are within the legislative domain.” (Article 38 of the Constitution of October 4, 1958, amended by Constitutional Law No. 2008-724 of July 23, 2008, modernizing the institutions of the Fifth Republic).

However, the Senate report of 2021 on the “proposed constitutional law guaranteeing respect for the principles of representative democracy and the rule of law in the event of legislation by ordinance” denounces the following developments:

“While the Government has always exercised this prerogative, its use has significantly increased in recent years, as evidenced by the Senate’s monitoring of ordinances. This structural trend of diminishing Parliament’s role is undesirable, especially since during the entire period of authorization, which has averaged eleven months since 2007, it is no longer allowed to legislate on the delegated matter. The figures indeed confirm the normalization of the use of

ordinances under Article 38 of the Constitution: 14 ordinances were published each year between 1984 and 2007; 30 per year between 2007 and 2012; 54 per year between 2012 and 2017; and 64 per year since 2017. During the 2019-2020 session, 100 ordinances were published (compared to 59 in the previous session), including 67 in response to the COVID-19 health crisis.” (Bas, 2021: 6)

Using ordinances in politics in France appears as a government tool that allows for quicker modifications of technical points. Beyond issues related to doping, this process highlights the supremacy given to the executive power over the legislative power, a trend that has been ongoing since the beginning of the Fifth Republic, which erodes the space for deliberation among elected representatives. Since the enactment in 2007 of the UNESCO International Convention against Doping in Sport, France’s anti-doping policy and the transposition of the World Anti-Doping Code into French domestic law have also relied on ordinances: Ordinance No. 2010-379 of April 14, 2010, concerning the health of athletes and the alignment of the sports code with the principles of the World Anti-Doping Code; Ordinance No. 2015-1207 of September 30, 2015, regarding legislative measures necessary to ensure compliance with the principles of the World Anti-Doping Code; Ordinance No. 2018-603 of July 11, 2018, regarding disciplinary procedures before the French Anti-Doping Agency; Ordinance No. 2018-1178 of December 19, 2018, regarding legislative measures necessary to complete the transposition of the principles of the World Anti-Doping Code into domestic law; and Ordinance No. 2021-488 of April 21, 2021, regarding legislative measures necessary to ensure the alignment of domestic law with the principles of the World Anti-Doping Code and enhance the effectiveness of the fight against doping.

This enumeration, by titles and dates, illustrates the pace at which France has conformed to the UNESCO Convention and, through it, the World Anti-Doping Code, as well as the nature of this compliance. Indeed, the objective has gradually shifted towards aligning the Sports Code

with the principles of the 2009 Code, followed by adopting necessary legislative measures to “ensure compliance” then to “perfect the transposition” of the 2015 World Code, and finally to “ensure the alignment of domestic law with the principles of the 2021 Code”. The increasing speed with which French lawmakers are addressing the need to comply with the new World Code in force is evident. On February 23, 2021, barely two months after the last version of the World Code came into effect, the law was enacted “empowering the Government to take the necessary legislative measures to ensure the alignment of domestic law with the principles of the World Anti-Doping Code and enhance the effectiveness of the fight against doping”, marking an unusually short timeframe that had never been adhered to or even sought before. In France, a rapid legislative process is thus taking place, fitting into a broader political dynamic, similar to the aforementioned senatorial report.

So, the period preceding the Paris Olympic and Paralympic Games is marked by three ordinances, two in 2018 and one in 2021. Ordinance of December 19, 2018, came into force on March 1, 2019. Notably, it removes the disciplinary authority of French sports federations (Chaussard 2019). This removal has two consequences in the following years. Firstly, this sanctioning power shifts to the French agency, which later entrusted it to a sanctions commission that is intended to be independent from the administration, the sports movement, and the AFLD’s board, for national constitutional reasons. Secondly, this removal leads to the strengthening of the federations’ competencies in the area of prevention, which can be viewed as a form of substitute jurisdiction – drawing here from Abbott’s (1988) notion of jurisdiction – especially as the officials from the AFLD’s Department of Education and Prevention work to train anti-doping representatives within the sports federations. Ordinance of April 21, 2021, reshapes the AFLD (Chaussard 2021) and grants it new prerogatives. Thus, the AFLD is notably tasked with establishing an anti-doping education program that must be respected and

implemented by compliance intermediaries such as sports federations and medical anti-doping prevention branches (AMPD).

Beyond the shift of sanctioning prerogatives from sports federations to the AFLD and the transfer of prevention responsibilities from the Ministry of Sports to the French agency, we are witnessing a profound reconfiguration of the allocation of competencies, the distribution of tasks, and consequently, the relationships between actors and their powers of action in the field of anti-doping.

Thus, the collusions highlighted in the press, in whistleblower testimonies, and in investigative reports during the described crisis period, in light of the upcoming Games, have legitimized the reactivation of demands from the World Anti-Doping Agency for France to establish an independent anti-doping laboratory separate from the French National Anti-Doping Organization. Created in 1966, the national anti-doping testing laboratory (LNDD), which became the anti-doping laboratory of Châtenay-Malabry and was integrated into the AFLD in 2006, has been known as the French Anti-Doping Laboratory (LADF) since January 1, 2022. It is now detached from the analysis department of the AFLD and affiliated with the University of Paris-Saclay.

Moreover, the new responsibilities regarding prevention at the AFLD, previously discussed, are accompanied as of July 31, 2019, by a new Investigations and Intelligence Department within the French agency. The expanded capabilities to combat trafficking in doping products introduce new concrete means of implementation: the authority to request any documents in the course of an investigation, to conduct facility visits, to use a fictitious identity online, etc. Furthermore, the recent promulgation by Emmanuel Macron of Organic Law No. 2022-400 aimed at enhancing the role of the Defender of Rights in reporting alerts, and Law No. 2022-401 aimed at improving whistleblower protection, published in Official Journal No. 68 on March 22, 2022, further extends the normalization process concerning whistleblowers in the

context of the organization of the 2024 Olympic and Paralympic Games in France. Finally, from a repressive perspective, while nighttime controls were previously applicable only in the context of counter-terrorism, Law No. 2023-380 of May 19, 2023, relating to the Olympic and Paralympic Games of 2024 and various other provisions, allows for nighttime controls between 11 PM and 5 AM under specific, serious conditions, particularly in cases of suspected evidence destruction. This so-called Olympic law also permits the examination of athletes' genetic characteristics for anti-doping purposes, thereby modifying not only the Sports Code but also the Civil Code.

These transformations reflect a political will to distinguish itself through strict compliance with the international requirements of the World Anti-Doping Agency, a private Swiss foundation. Moreover, these evolutions illustrate a constrained but accepted agenda. This alignment work relies both on established legal and political mechanisms at the national level and necessitates and justifies constitutional modifications. The OPG then constitute a host context that requires overcoming any form of resistance, seeking pathways to compatibility, and addressing the issue of the inadequacy of structures to the imported solution (James and Lodge 2003). Among these “public action solutions” (Delpeuch 2009: 154-155), the production of legislative texts organizes the redistribution of prerogatives among the ministry, the French agency, Paris Saclay University, the federations, etc., creating the illusion of easily interchangeable roles and horizontal internal transfers.

The AFLD does not make decisions and does not hold public authority prerogatives. However, the competencies that have been reassigned to it and the investigative powers entrusted to it, in its capacity as a signatory of the World Anti-Doping Code, disrupt the concrete implementation methods of the previously existing anti-doping policy in France (Demeslay and Chaussard 2020). It seems that the fight against doping in sports, continuing from a proactive regulatory

approach open to international influences and in the catalytic context of the Paris 2024 Games, has become the subject of a public policy in the sense that it no longer falls solely under a “systemic” agenda that encompasses all the issues and problems commonly perceived by members of the political community as deserving public attention but rather under an “institutional” agenda that covers all items that are explicitly taken into serious and active account by decision-makers (Cobb and Elder 1983: 14-15).

Inherited reputation

“The French national anti-doping organization is henceforth positioned alongside its most effective European counterparts, in the context of France hosting major sporting events, such as the recent Rugby World Cup and the upcoming Paris 2024 Olympic and Paralympic Games.” (AFLD 2023). International events held on national territory serve as moments for showcasing the strengths and weaknesses of a state, thus providing particular moments of exposure to evaluation by global actors. This excerpt signifies a desire to highlight a significant movement in the periodic process of harmonizing anti-doping regulations and aligning France with international standards. The use of the adverb *henceforth* “linguistically presupposes a break from a prior state of affairs” or, more accurately, “the crossing of a threshold in a progressive process” due to the attainment of a level “considered particularly significant” (Chateauraynaud and Doury 2010). Given France’s historical positioning regarding anti-doping legislation on the international stage, one might be surprised by the expression of this rupture. Nonetheless, it formalizes the political stakes and distinctions at play in anti-doping efforts, attests to the existence of national rankings of organizations, reflects the significance of “agencies” in international political life, which can act, as is the case here, as transfer entrepreneurs in the sense of actively engaging with political-administrative decision-makers (Delpeuch 2009: 158).

This “positioning” at the European level, indexed on budgetary and human resources allocated to anti-doping efforts and recognition of expertise, signifies a quest for excellence and prestige, thus belonging to what Paradeise and Thoenig have referred to as the elite (2011). Moreover, one cannot help but recall Weber’s assertion that “Anyone who does not adapt their conduct to the conditions of capitalist success will perish or, at the very least, will not rise very high” (Weber 1964: 75). The political, legal, institutional, and practical work to align with the expectations of the World Anti-Doping Agency reveals the French state’s strategies for importing international norms in a context increasingly marked by evaluation. Evaluations through audits, questionnaires from UNESCO, WADA, and the Council of Europe, along with assessments of France during the Games in both formal and informal settings, give maximum weight to a worldview. These conformity evaluations, due to their proliferation, juxtaposition, recurrence, and strong interconnection in all documents, actor networks, and objects outlined by the regulatory framework for combating doping in sports, can be understood from the emitters’ perspective as “persuasion techniques”. Thus, evaluation in its broadest sense, amplified during the organization of a major event like the Olympic and Paralympic Games, serves as a governance tool contributing to political expression power.

This quest for prestige and excellence thus motivates the choice to transpose norms more than the virtues of the solution itself (Dupré 2003). Once again, the hybridity of the theoretical frameworks is heuristic. Building on studies of Europeanization, analyzing this process reveals that the mobilization of internal instruments and mechanisms, along with the reconfiguration of competencies in favor of importing provisions from the Code and the WADA standards, both expresses and reinforces a process of integration beyond the national scale. However, by employing other conceptual frameworks, positioning oneself among the strong links in the chain of anti-doping regulation at the international level appears to be a way to resymmetrize power relations. Indeed, multiple reasons underlie these transfers. On one hand, their analysis

reveals a controlling relationship exerted by the WADA over the AFLD and, consequently, on the French state, which provides justifications at the national level for transforming anti-doping policy and the relationships between actors. On the other hand, these transfers demonstrate national actors committed to the cause and position France as a model for other countries precisely because of its ability to find ways to translate the international model.

From these perspectives, the fight against doping represents a field of expression for appropriating international norms, illustrating a proactive policy of entering and maintaining “in the ranks”, thereby becoming a unique and crucial domain where being on the leaderboard is essential for establishing reputation.

Conclusion

The organization of the Olympic and Paralympic Games in France in 2024 has swiftly brought forth the notion of legacy, characterized by its plural and ambiguous contours. This contribution analyzes the political repercussions of the Paris Games in the realm of anti-doping.

While not exhaustive regarding the multiple transformations undertaken to distinguish oneself in the realm of compliance, this article presents the fight against doping as a trial, concurrent with the preparation of athletes, reflective of the international political competition in which sports are merely one facet of expression. The systematization of mechanisms for incorporating international provisions through ordinances, the revision of constitutional elements of national law – such as night-time controls – the redistribution of anti-doping prerogatives, which redefine labor relations and the structural and functional public/private mesh, and the adoption of an “institutional” agenda (Cobb and Elder 1983) all represent the initial legacies of the Games for France and affirm the political catalytic role of this event.

Assuming a conceptual hybridity that combines *policy transfer studies*, actor-network theory, and pragmatic sociology, the transfers of anti-doping norms studied reflect both the asymmetric

power relations between international and national organizations, as well as between the private and public spheres (including at the national level in France) – justifying the subversive nature of the importation of norms – and highlight the challenges of re-symmetrizing these relations. Timed, observed, judged, and measured, anti-doping policy has emerged as a domain where France – the state, and its National Anti-Doping Organization – could not afford to fail in maintaining its reputation.

In the described process, the focus is not merely on borrowing but on transposition and transplantation, with the primary aim of faithfully reproducing a model even before addressing a political issue. This strict transposition serves to enhance the reputation of the French state while, more subtly, undermining the legitimacy of all the frameworks and modalities of public action in the context of reception (Delpeuch 2009: 164). Consequently, this article reinforces the idea that we should not overestimate the obstacles generated by the divergence of cultures and traditions (Delpeuch 2009: 162); the significance of the event allows for the cognitive obstacle and forms of conceptual incompatibility to be diminished. In this regard, analyzing the consequences of the OPG on French anti-doping policy will benefit from the collection of data that enables access to the implementation and reception of the transfers made. In other words, it aims to study the “success of the transplant” (Delpeuch 2009: 154) and to account for the significance of the new forms of connectivity produced.

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